

A NEW CLASS OF THE THERMOTROPIC LIQUID CRYSTAL POLYMER: POLY(ARYL ETHER KETONE)S

Shanju Zhang¹, Yubin Zheng¹, Zhongwen Wu¹, Decai Yang², Ryutoku Yosomiya³

¹*Department of Chemistry, Jilin University, Changchun, 130023, P.R.China*

²*Polymer Physics Laboratory, Changchun Institute of Applied Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Changchun, 130022, P.R.China*

³*Department of Industrial Chemistry, Chiba Institute of Technology, 2-17-1, Tsudanuma Narashino, Chiba, 275 Japan*

SUMMARY: The novel poly(aryl ether ketone)s containing chloro-side group were synthesized by nucleophilic substitution reactions of 4,4'-biphenol and chlorohydroquinone with either 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone (BP/CH/DF) or 1,4-bis(p-fluorobenzoyl)benzene (BP/CH/BF) and their thermotropic liquid crystalline properties were characterized by a variety of experimental techniques. The mesogen/hydroxy-quinone ratio is varied in the copolymers and the thermotropic liquid crystalline behavior was observed in the copolymers containing 50 and 70% biphenol. DSC results indicate that the copolymers had two melting transitions. The lower temperature transitions represent the crystal-to-liquid crystal transitions (T_m) while the higher temperature transitions refer to the liquid crystal-to-isotropic transitions (T_i). A banded texture was formed after shearing the sample in the liquid crystalline state. The novel poly(aryl ether ketone)s had relatively higher glass transition temperature (T_g) and lower melting temperature (T_m).

KEYWORDS: thermotropic liquid crystal polymer, poly(aryl ether ketone)s synthesis, liquid crystal behavior

INTRODUCTION

Poly(aryl ether ketone)s have been found very useful as advanced materials in applications because of their excellent thermal stability and good chemical resistance. However, poly(aryl ether ketone)s have several limitations in processing due to high melting temperature and high melt viscosities (1). Thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers (TLCP) are known to have melt viscosities significantly lower than structurally similar isotropic polymers. Furthermore, the TLCP materials exhibit anisotropy in extruded and molded articles as a result of preferential orientation of LCP domains or individual chains (2). Although 4,4'-biphenol-based homopoly(aryl ether ketone)s have been shown no liquid crystal properties, copolymers based on a crystal-disrupting monomer and a mesogenic biphenyl monomer may be an effective method to synthesize thermotropic poly(aryl ether ketone)s. Recently, Bennett and Farris (3) reported the synthesis and characterization of the novel thermotropic liquid crystalline poly(aryl ether ketone)s. These materials have potential applications as engineering thermoplastics or fibers. In addition, the materials may be useful as processing aids or reinforcing agents in blending with isotropic poly(aryl ether ketone)s. In this work, a series of thermotropic liquid crystalline poly(aryl ether ketone)s based on chlorohydroquinone and

biphenyl mesogen with either 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone or 1,4-bis(p-fluorobenzoyl)benzene were synthesized by the nucleophilic substitution reaction and characterized by several experimental techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The material 4,4'-biphenol was obtained from Honshu Kaggaku Ltd. in the highest available purity. Chlorohydroquinone (Tokyo Kasei Co. Ltd.) was recrystallized from chloroform. Anhydrous potassium carbonate was ground and dried in an oven at 150°C. The xylene and tetramethylene sulfone (TMSO₂) were distilled under vacuum before use. 4,4'-difluorobenzophenone and 1,4-bis(p-fluorobenzoyl)benzene were prepared in our laboratory by the standard procedures.

Synthesis

The synthesis route of the copolymers is illustrated in a schematic (Fig.1). In a typical procedure, a three-necked flask was outfit with a platinum thermometer, nitrogen inlet, magnetic stirrer and a Dean-Stark trap. Appropriate mole ratio of the monomers were added into the reactor under nitrogen atmosphere. The temperature was slowly raised to 160°C over a period of 3h to allow phenolate formation and water / xylene azeotrope distillation which was collected in the trap. Subsequently the reaction temperature gradually raised to 200-220°C for polymerization over a period of 8h. The resulting polymer was separated by precipitation of the reaction mixture in methanol. The crude product was purified by hot methanol and water.

Fig.1: The synthesis route of poly(aryl ether ketone) copolymers

Characterization

The thermal analysis was carried out with a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7 instrument. The temperatures and heat flow scales were carefully calibrated by using standard materials indium and tin over a wide temperature range. Heating and cooling rates of 10/min were used under nitrogen atmosphere and the maximum of endotherm was taken as the transition temperature. A polarizing light microscope (PLM) of Opton R Pol was used for texture characterization of the copolymer samples. The wide angle x-ray diffraction (WAXD) was carried out in Japan D/max-γA X-ray instrument (Cu Kα radiation). The inherent viscosities of the copolymers were measured in a mixed solvent of p-chlorophenol/1,1,2,2-

tetrachloroethane at 45°C. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed in a Perkin-Elmer TGA7 thermogravimetric analyser, using a heating rate of 20°C/min in nitrogen atmosphere.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data of the thermal properties are collected in Table 1. All of the copolymers had higher glass transition temperatures (T_g) between 160°C and 200°C as determined by DSC. The thermal stability (T_d) were also measured by TGA in the range of 430 ~ 520°C. The biphenol-based homopoly(aryl ether ketone)s, 100BP/100DF and 100BP/100BF, had one melting transitions(T_m). PLM results show that they have no birefringence above their T_m s. The side chains homopoly(aryl ether ketone)s, 100CH/100DF, and 100CH/100BF, had one glassy transition temperature(T_g). WAXD results show that they are amorphous polymers. Copolymers based on a crystal-disrupting diene-goup monomer and a mesogenic biphenyl monomer is an effective method to synthesize thermotropic liquid crystal poly(aryl ether ketone)s. The thermotropic liquid crystal behavior was observed in the copolymers containing 50 and 70% biphenol. As expected, each of the copolymers had relatively lower melting transition T_m (290 ~ 340°C) than the isotropic poly(aryl ether ketone) containing biphenyl because of the copolymerization effect of the side-group monomer. Both the crystalline-to-LC transitions (T_m) and the LC-to-isotropic transitions (T_i) were observed in the DSC thermograms of the copolymers, which were further confirmed by PLM observation. As the content of nonmesogenic comonomer units increased, the crystalline-to-LC transition (T_m) became broader and of lesser intensity. The later was indicated by the decrease in heat of fusion (ΔH_m) in Table 1.

For further characterization of the thermotropic liquid crystalline behavior, the copolymers were evaluated by visual observations on PLM. The thin samples were heated at 400°C for a few minutes, subsequently cooled slowly to liquid crystalline state and annealed at the temperature for 1h, and then quenched to room temperature.

Table 1: Thermal Properties of The Novel Copolymers

Sample	n	x	T_g (°C)	T_m (°C)	T_i (°C)	ΔH_m (kJ/g)	ΔH_i (kJ/g)	T_d (°C)
100BP/100DF	0	0	181	409	---	169	---	520
70BP/30CH/100DF	0	0.3	168	338	368	115	6	430
50BP/50CH/100DF	0	0.5	185	336	350	19	19	458
30BP/70CH/100DF	0	0.7	183	328	---	7	---	476
100CH/100DF	0	1	158	---	---	---	---	480
100BP/100BF	1	0	183	412	---	153	---	520
70BP/30CH/100BF	1	0.3	197	318	353	34	11	487
50BP/50CH/100BF	1	0.5	190	289	314	9	26	490
30BP/70CH/100BF	1	0.7	165	308	---	4	---	480
100CH/100BF	1	1	163	---	---	---	---	485

Fig.2a shows a photomicrograph of copolymer 70BP/30CH/100DF isothermally heat treated at 330°C for 1h. It displays a threaded texture, which is often found in the nematic phase. However, after the mechanical shearing and slight relaxation banded texture can be observed. The formation of banded textures after shearing is nearly ubiquitous for nematic polymers (7,8) (Fig.2b). This banded texture which is perpendicular to the shear direction has a width of

about $2\mu\text{m}$. For the copolymer 50BP/50CH/100DF, a second type of texture, fanlike texture, has been observed, which was recorded at room temperature after annealing the sample at 300°C for 1h and then air quenching (Fig.3). This fanlike texture shows that the copolymer 50BP/50CH/100DF has a ordered smectic phase.

Furthermore, the copolymer 70BP/30CH/100BF exhibited threaded texture, while the copolymer 50BP/50CH/100BF showed fanlike texture, too. The above results are well consistent to the results of DSC. Cooling the copolymer 70BP/30CH/100BF from 400°C at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ resulted in the formation of threaded texture at 350°C (Fig.4a) and fanlike texture at 290°C (Fig.4b). Quenching the copolymer from 400°C resulted in another fanlike texture(Fig.4c). The reason is not known now. The copolymer 50BP/50CH/100BF formed the plate-like texture at 290°C (Fig.5). It is interesting to mention here that micrometer-size monodomains may also form in the copolymer 70BP/30CH/100BF in LC state under a strong mechanical, periodic shear force field (Fig.6). In general, one way to obtain monodomain in liquid crystalline polymers is to develop a homogenous orientation of the chain directors parallel to the substrate surface. Mechanical shearing may result in a homogeneous orientation in which the mesogenic moieties lie parallel to the substrate surface (9). Although molecular connectivity between the mesogenic moieties in liquid crystalline polymers may significantly affect this orientation process, the monodomain of nematic polymer has also been achieved by Cheng et al. under strong shearing (10).

Fig.2: Optical micrographs of the copolymer 70BP/30CH/100DF after cooling from 400°C to 330°C and annealing for 1h and then quenching to room temperature, (a) without mechanical shearing and (b) with mechanical shearing. The arrow shows the shear direction.

CONCLUSION

The thermotropic liquid crystallinity can be achieved in the novel poly(aryl ether ketone)s. The copolymers containing 70% and 50% biphenol mesogen showed nematic and smectic texture, respectively. These copolymers may be of interest as potential engineering thermoplastics, fibers or films with unique anisotropic properties.

Fig 3: Optical micrograph of the sample 50BP/50CH/100DF after cooling from 400 °C to 300 °C and annealing for 1h and then quenching to room temperature.

Fig 4: Optical micrograph of the sample 70BP/30CH/100BF after cooling from 400 °C to (a)350 °C (b)290 °C (c)room temperature.

Fig.5: Optical micrograph of the sample 50BP/50CH/100BF after cooling from 400 to 290 and annealing for 1h and then quenching to room temperature.

Fig.6: The monodomain of the copolymer 70BP/30CH/100BF after strong mechanical shearing at 350 and then air quenching. The arrow shows the shear direction.

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